

The Role of Classroom Management Skill in Directing Achievement Guidance Among Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the role of classroom management skills in directing achievement guidance among secondary school students in Wasit Governorate. It was revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the level of identifying classroom problems due to variables of type, specialization, and professional experience of the person in charge of the classroom management process. The descriptive analytical method was used to suit the research's nature and the data type obtained. The research community consisted of 200 male and female teachers from various schools in Wasit Governorate and approximately 6 schools that teach the secondary stage. In order to be involved in collecting data and obtaining the necessary information centered around classroom management, a random sample of 22 teachers were selected. In order to collect data for the study, the researcher used the research tool (questionnaire) to measure the level of classroom problems. It consisted of 16 items, and in order to verify the validity of the tool, virtual validity was used by seeking the opinions of arbitrators with experience in the field of classroom management who have experience from Those who have worked in the field of classroom management for long periods and have a lot of information and theories related to the current study. The reliability of the questionnaire was verified using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and its value was 0.82, which is high and excellent stability for applying the questionnaire items to the research sample. To analyze the data, the researcher used weighted arithmetic means, percentages, standard deviations, and the discrimination coefficient, and when calculating the value of (t), the results of the study showed that the degree of exposure of male and female secondary school teachers to classroom problems was average in the total score in the seven dimensions of the scale. It also became clear that there were statistically significant differences in exposure to classroom problems due to the scientific and literary specialization variable and gender, males, and females.

Keywords: *classroom management skills, education process, leadership, professional growth.*

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Introduction

The education process is going through essential turning points, as it has undergone significant developments in all its aspects, whether about the curriculum, the teacher, school administration, classroom management, and guidance methods, so each has become comprehensive for all aspects of the educational process (Tafesh, 2004, p. 11).

One of the most critical aspects of this process is classroom management and its influential role in the educational field, as it is considered of great importance because it constitutes a fundamental axis in serving our educational process. It receives excellent attention from all officials and researchers in this field because of its significant impact on improving the process. Educational workers, as those working in the field of education, like other fields of life, need skills and competencies in classroom management so that their work can develop for the better, keep up with everything new, increase the level of service they perform, and so that their production increases and their value increases. (Al-Affendi, 1990, p. 17)

This is what studies and research have confirmed, as they stated that the teacher needs a set of skills in the teaching method, the most important of which is classroom management, in order to master the methods of dealing with students, gain experience in the teaching profession, and achieve educational goals. (Attari et al., 2005, p. 377)

Classroom management is a directed activity that depends on studying the educational situation and aims to serve all those working in the field of education to unleash and develop the capabilities of teachers in an educational reality that achieves the desired educational goals. (Ministry of Education, 1998, p. 4)

This prompted the researcher to conduct the current research, the problems of which can be summarized in the following question:

- What is the role of classroom management skills in directing achievement guidance among teachers at the secondary stage?
- Is this what the research will try to answer?

Teaching skills today have taken on new dimensions and means, and methods have been developed to target specific points in conveying information to secondary school students.

Educational literature pays great attention to the role of skills and methods for the educational teacher due to their organic connection to improving the teaching and learning processes by raising students' efficiency in receiving concepts and improving their achievement levels. This is directly reflected in exam results and progress in understanding, assimilating, and mastering lesson topics.

As for the field of achievement guidance, recent research and studies in the field of education have shown the influential role that skills play in conveying the material to

students' minds. These research studies uniquely looked at the teacher, aiming to know the extent of his success in reaching the set goals. This led to a noticeable improvement in the organization's methods. Likewise, the skill and mastery of it are considered to be the competence of each teacher and a measure of the extent of his productivity, the extent of his interest in the tasks entrusted to them, and the extent of the influence of all of this on the behavior of his students, and his success in performing his work. Achievement guidance is considered one of the most critical tasks the teacher must carry out before presenting the material. The processes of guidance, warning, and continuous feedback to the student have become essential matters in the educational process to help the student be more effective in receiving the lesson topics and activating the role of positive competition among students.

Research Importance

In the preceding, the importance of the research can be summarized in the following points:

1. It gave special importance to the educational teacher's leadership behavior and his effective role in developing the personal behavior of students, who are the focus of the educational process.
2. The developments and changes that took place in the teaching field emphasized the importance and, at the same time, imposed new conditions on the teacher. These developments and changes opened broad horizons for him, introducing methods and innovations that fit the goals he seeks to achieve.
3. A competent teacher must understand the role played by the teaching process and the task it performs, as well as research methods related to teaching so that he can serve the educational process honestly and successfully
4. Great interest in the role of teaching skills and methods due to their fundamental connection to improving the teaching and learning processes
5. Achievement guidance for the student is one of the most important tasks that the teacher performs before giving the lesson, helping the teacher be more effective in his educational work.

Search Objectives

The current research aims to identify the role of classroom management skills in directing achievement guidance among secondary school students.

Research Limits

The current research is limited to several male and female teachers working in Essaouira Education, affiliated with the Wasit Education Directorate, for the academic year 2023-2024.

Literature Review

The Concept of Classroom Management Skills

There are many definitions of what classroom management skills deal with in many aspects, and they vary due to the diversity of philosophies, theories, and stages, their definitions, their familiarity with its aspects, and their analysis of its framework and content. Some of them limit it to directing instruction inside the classroom and appreciating the work of teachers. Some of them limit it to directing education inside

the classroom and appreciating the work of teachers, and some of them limit it to providing the teacher with the help he needs. Some aim to provide students at all levels with better educational services.

Management in the Language

The meaning of administration has been mentioned in (Laslin al-Arab) as:

Whoever managed: he became at the forefront and rose in opinion. He managed something: he took control of it and surrounded its features.

Classroom management: The place where information is delivered in various forms to provide the student with valuable, helpful information free of ambiguity. He turned the thing around and looked at it from above (Ibn Manzur, 1968, p. 137).

Classroom Management in Terms

Muhammad Ziyad Hamdan defines it as a "sharp" or "super" vision of behavior and things capable of identifying their strengths and weaknesses and then proposing appropriate therapeutic solutions. (Hamdan, 1992, p. 10)

Jawdat Atwi points out that educators agree that the classroom management process is a specialized technical service that a teacher provides to the students he teaches to improve their achievement level. (Atwi, 2001, p. 330).

Nashwan, (1992) states, "a series of interactions and events that occur between the teacher and the student inside the classroom, which is work that has its educational inputs and outputs, and the outputs are supposed to be better than before." (Nashwan, 1992, p. 12)

Morsi, (1995) as "a living, dynamic, evolving concept that aims to guide and guide the student to help him develop himself, develop his level of performance, and thus raise the level of the educational process as a whole." (Morsi, 1995, p. 368)

Al-Ibrahim, (2002) as "an interactive process between the teacher and the student in a democratic atmosphere that aims to provide the teacher with everything that achieves his scientific and professional growth to improve the learning and teaching processes." (Al-Ibrahim, 2002, p. 14)

Al-Ta'ani, (2005) as "a cooperative, leadership, democratic, and organized process concerned with educational and learning situations with all its elements, including curricula, means, methods, the environment of the teacher and learner, school administration, and all the factors that influence, evaluate, and organize those positions in order to achieve the goals of the educational process." (Al-Ta'ani, 2005, p. 19)

Classroom management was defined by the researcher for the purposes of research as "a cooperative process that requires the presence of specific competencies and skills possessed by the teacher, which takes place between the educational teacher and the student, and it cannot bear fruit except through this cooperation whose goal is to develop the student's level through the various methods that the educational teacher presents to the student to achieve.

Theoretical Background

The skill of classroom management is of great importance. Since it is considered one of the essential pillars on which the teaching and learning process is based, it is considered a sponsor of that process in all its aspects and elements (the subject, the student, and the teaching method). It aims to work towards improving the educational

process by extending a hand. Aid and assistance to the teacher is considered the foundation upon which the teaching and learning process is based because of his pivotal role in serving the students. Through this pedagogy, he seeks to know what surrounds the educational process, works to modify and develop it, and sets goals to achieve them through a specific method.

Classroom Management Skill Objectives

Among the most prominent objectives of the classroom management skill are (Hassan & Awadallah, 2006, pp. 23-26) as follows:

- Helping the student enhance strengths and address weaknesses
- Events of change in the student's level of learning and understanding
- Clarifying the goals of education.
- Linking academic subjects.
- Enhancing feedback aspects
- Evaluating teaching results.

Atwi (2004, p. 232) stated the following goals:

- Developing the school curriculum regarding objectives, content, the teaching and learning method, and the evaluation method.
- Organizing the educational learning situation.
- Helping teachers develop their abilities and competencies to achieve educational goals.
- Creating change and educational development.
- Improving school conditions and environment.
- Developing the school's relationship with the local environment.

As for (Al-Munif, 2004, p. 54), it has the following objectives:

- Diagnosing the educational situation and identifying strengths and weaknesses.
- Improving the level of professional teacher performance.
- Introducing teachers to effective teaching methods.
- Encouraging teachers to engage in educational research and field experiences.
- Overcoming the difficulties and obstacles facing the teacher
- Provide and familiarize the teacher with effective evaluation methods.
- Paying attention to the psychological and professional needs of teachers.
- Developing human relations among teachers.
- Introducing teachers to classroom management methods.
- Evaluating teachers and providing them with feedback.

From what was previously mentioned regarding the objectives of educational supervision, it becomes clear that there are differences in viewpoints regarding defining these objectives. However, everyone agreed that these objectives focus on assisting the teacher and improving the educational process in all its aspects.

Teaching Skill Jobs

The functions of teaching skills, as defined by Sahar Badoud (2009), can be summarized as follows:

Administrative jobs

- Cooperating with school students in the process of understanding the content of the subject.
- Participate in the classroom question and answer process.
- Focus on the educational system and atmosphere.
- Prepare the blackboard adequately and highlight the most critical points of the lesson.
- Providing the appropriate administrative climate for students' growth and achieving the goals of the educational process.

Refreshing functions

- Urging the student to scientific and educational production.
- Helping students in self-development.
- Helping to employ educational techniques and teaching aids.

Training jobs

Teachers pledge to teach for their growth and improve their performance levels and thus improve the educational situation through workshops, research seminars, bulletins, and helping teachers develop the educational program and understand educational goals.

Research jobs

- Sensing the problems that hinder the educational process, seeking to identify them, and thinking seriously about solving them
- Forming a research team in each school to study the problems of the subject, students, and administration.

Evaluative functions

- Measuring the extent to which the teacher's work is compatible with the educational institution's goals, curricula, and directions.
- Identify the strengths in the teacher's performance and enhance them; discover the weak points and treat and remedy them.
- Assist in evaluating the educational process on accurate, objective foundations.

Analytical functions

- Providing teachers with information on analyzing curricula according to theoretical models for curriculum analysis and development.
- Analyze the curriculum regarding objectives, content, teaching methods, and evaluation.
- Analyzing test questions through their specific technical specifications.

Innovative functions

- Creating new ideas and methods used to develop the educational process.
- Putting these ideas and methods to the test and experimentation.
- Generalizing these ideas and methods after testing them and proving their validity (Badaoud, 2009, pp. 28-29).

Duties of the Classroom Manager

The classroom director performs various tasks, including effective classroom management, to confront the problems of weak academic achievement, weak motivation for learning, and gaps in the curriculum. Among the most important of these tasks are what he mentioned (Abu Abed, 2005, pp. 177-185):

- Professional development of learners.
- Organizing and managing in-service training programs.
- Evaluating the educational process and analyzing educational performance.
- Conducting educational studies and research.
- Taking care of the mental health of teachers and learners.
- Evaluation of teaching/learning materials

Al-Mughaidi, (2001: p. 41) mentioned the following tasks:

- Helping the learner understand the goals of education, the school, the subject he is studying, how to formulate educational goals, and how to achieve them.
- Study the factors that hinder the learning process among students.
- Study new educational methods related to the curriculum.
- Motivating teachers to think and experiment on sound scientific foundations.
- Supporting group cooperation among learners to achieve the desired goals.
- Diagnosing learners' areas of creativity and working to develop them.
- Justice in distributing competencies to schools.

Achievement Guidance Methods

Classroom management methods have evolved according to the development of the concept of achievement supervision. Many and varied methods have emerged, and each method has its advantages and uses, as well as conditions that must be met for its success.

In light of the modern concept, academic supervision is considered an integrated work program that aims to improve the teaching and learning processes by providing a helping hand to all workers in the field of education using various methods. (Al-Badri, 2002, p. 55).

Muhammad Jawad Al-Khatib believes that these methods are: "a group of aspects of educational activity carried out by the educational supervisor, teacher, students, and school principals in order to achieve the goals of effective classroom management and educational supervision." (Al-Khatib, 2005, p. 239)

The educational literature has dealt with many divisions of achievement supervision methods, the most important of which is the division in terms of target groups that he mentioned. (Al-Taani, 2005: p. 67). It is as follows:

Individual theoretical guidance methods:

They take the nature of theoretical decisions and target the teacher individually:

A- Directed readings.

B- Educational bulletin.

Group theoretical supervisory methods:

They take the character of theoretical talk, target a group of teachers, and include:

A - Educational seminars.

B- Educational conference.

C - Training course.

D - Action research.

Individual scientific supervisory methods:

They tend towards the practical side more than the theoretical and target the teacher individually, and include:

A- Individual meeting with the teacher.

B- The teacher's class visit.

Group practical supervisory methods: provide teachers with opportunities for field application and are carried out for a group of teachers collectively, and include:

A - Group meetings with teachers.

B - Educational workshop (educational workshop).

C - Micro-learning.

D - Illustrative (practical) lesson.

E - Exchange of visits between teachers.

Rafidah Al-Hariri defines it as: "A method through which the supervisor encourages teachers to develop the educational process through analysis and study of the educational problems and issues they face, then using the scientific method to solve those issues by extracting results and recommendations." (Al-Hariri, 2006: 32).

(Abu Abed, 2005: 120) believes that directed reading requires the educational supervisor to arouse the teachers' interest, encourage them to self-read, and recommend that they read specific educational articles or books during his meeting with them. He will see different responses from the teachers, and Al-Ta'ani confirms (Al-Ta'ani, 2005, p. 68) that the school principal must cooperate with the educational supervisor to determine the most critical readings and books that they prefer for teachers to see and that are useful in developing their knowledge and skills.

Educational bulletin

The educational bulletin is a supervisory media that saves time and effort if it is carefully prepared, well organized, and departs from the circle of routine and issuing instructions. Jawdat Atwi defined it as: "a written means of communication between

the supervisor and the teachers, through which the supervisor can convey to the teachers a summary of his readings, suggestions, and observations to the extent of a reasonable amount of time and effort." (Atwi, 2001: 292)

Educational symposium

It is a purposeful group activity in which several specialists present different aspects of a specific problem or topic to a group of teachers. A purposeful discussion about the presented ideas and opinions often follows the presentation. (Al-Saud, 2003: 264).

The educational symposium has many objectives, including what Al-Khatib (2005: 274) mentioned in the following points:

- Presenting the experiences of a group of people (from three to six), allowing the participant to compare and distinguish between different opinions and trends.
- Providing an excellent opportunity to exchange opinions and improve communication between participants and course members, as well as between participants and each other.
- Providing a type of change that helps attract participants' attention and increase their enthusiasm for the topic.

Educational Conference

A general meeting will be held for those interested in the educational process, including supervisors and teachers. Participants will exchange experiences on issues and matters that concern them in an effort to find appropriate educational solutions. (Al-Khatib et al., 1987: 240)

Educational conferences are among the rarest supervisory methods employed by educational supervisors because they are financially costly and require much time and effort in planning, preparation, and follow-up. However, they open the way for the most significant number of teachers to learn about new and diverse experiences through working papers presented by competent specialists in which they address a topic. Each worksheet is followed by a purposeful discussion in which teachers participate actively. (Abu Abed, 2005: 115).

From the above, it is clear that the style of educational seminars and conferences is similar in terms of organization and procedures, except that the conference is on a larger scale, as the number of participants in its presentation is more than six experts, and it may extend for several days.

Training course

Training courses are considered a supervisory method that updates teachers' information, develops them, and improves their performance through training and exposure to the latest teaching methods and educational methods. Hassan Al-Tani defines them as a supervisory activity supervised by the educational supervisor or director, aiming to change teachers' behavior, improve their performance, and raise their productive competencies. (Al-Tani, 2005: 70)

Mahmoud Abu Abed called them training seminars and described them as "a planned and organized training medium, which aims to enable trainees to acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities, enabling them to perform a specific job and to bring about a positive change in their attitudes towards work and the institution in which they work." (Abu Abed, 2005: 102)

Obstacles to Academic Supervision

There are obstacles that academic supervision faces during its supervision practices and that affect its performance as Al-Habib (1996: 86) indicated that the most critical problems of academic supervision are:

- A - Lack of means and work capabilities available to supervisors.
- B - The large number of tasks and the large number of teachers.
- C - Technical problems such as the difficulty of objective evaluation.
- D - Problems of relationships between the supervisor and the teacher and between the supervisor and the director.

Areas of administration in academic supervision

It is represented, as defined by Mahmoud Tafesh, as follows:

A - Planning: - which is characterized by innovation and innovation. The creative supervisor prepares his supervisory plan in cooperation with the teachers and helps them prepare their plans.

B - Students: - It is the goal of the educational process, so the role of students changed from that of the recipient of knowledge to that of researcher, discussant, and interlocutor, and attention was paid to it from all physical, mental, emotional, moral, and mental aspects in order to achieve the integrated growth of the student.

C - Teachers: - The scholar is the engine of the educational process. He is an organizer, a leader, and a discussion guide. Therefore, the supervisor should be interested in observing and developing the teachers' performance.

D—Curricula and textbooks: The role of the supervisor is to formulate the contents of the curricula, enrich them, and develop them to suit the needs of students and society's requirements.

E—Teaching methods: Proper teaching method selection requires special skills that teachers must be trained to consider individual differences among students, and the educational supervisor plays a major role in encouraging teachers to use them.

F—Educational activities and methods: The educational supervisor is required to train teachers on how to prepare educational methods appropriate to the educational situation. They also need to be trained on how to choose the educational activity that accompanies each goal that requires achieving it.

G—Evaluation: Evaluation is considered the basis for judging the tools of any educational situation and determining its strengths and weaknesses. (Tafesh, 2004, p. 87)

Types of achievement supervision in effective classroom management

Achievement supervision has different types, and each type is determined by various factors and variables. Perhaps the most important of these is the person in charge of managing the classroom itself and the goals and tasks he sets for his work and believes he must perform.

Areas of administration in academic supervision

Mahmoud Tafesh pointed out that educational researchers have indicated several classifications for academic supervision, including: -

- Classification according to the approach into participatory, clinical, and supervision by objectives.
- Classification according to the supervisor's style into authoritarian, diplomatic, missionary, and democratic supervision.
- Classification according to its results into corrective, preventive, constructive, and creative supervision (Tafesh, 2004, p. 80)

Fikri Rayan also classified it according to the way the supervisor performs his duties:

- Supervising the inspection level.
- Supervising the level of assistance and assistance.
- Supervising the level of cooperation.
- Supervising the level of social democratic leadership. (Ryan, 1988: 9)

Classification of achievement supervision in classroom management according to goals and means:

Corrective supervision

It is a type of supervision related to the purpose of the educational supervision process. This type seeks to correct the teacher's mistakes without offending them or doubting his ability to teach. Many supervisors are interested in catching the teacher's mistakes from their work sites and consider this one of their primary jobs.

The mistakes that a teacher makes while performing his work are of two types:

1- Simple errors: These are formal errors rather than fundamental and appear in the teacher's actions, such as incorrect pronunciation of some words or the teacher taking an inappropriate sitting or standing position.

2-Physical errors: These are those that misdirect the student's development or may negatively affect their personalities.

In both cases, the supervisor provides the necessary treatment to solve the problem. (Al-Bustan, 2003: 355)

Preventive academic supervision

The educational supervisor has gained experience while working as a teacher or while visiting teachers and observing their teaching methods. Therefore, he can predict the new teacher's difficulties and the methods that lead to his embarrassment and anxiety. Here, the supervisor follows methods that are appropriate to the situation. It helps the teacher avoid difficulties; thus, this type protects the teacher from losing his self-confidence and allows him to face new situations. (Al-Saud, 2002: 58).

Constructive achievement supervision

The educational supervisor and teacher focus on the future and work on growth, evaluation, and improvement of the learning process at the primary and secondary levels. (Abdul Hadi, 2002: 40)

The supervisor must not mention the error or point it out to them unless he has alternative proposals to replace the old, faulty old with the good. The beginning of supervision is a clear vision of the educational goals and the means to achieve them to the greatest extent.

Creative achievement supervision

It is a distinctive type of supervision, which encourages supervisors to adopt it because it unleashes energies, stimulates motivation, improves appreciation of the importance of human relations between teachers, and exploits their energies, talents, and abilities to achieve goals by working in a team spirit. It also works to form conscious and loyal educational leaders and to be the supervisor. He must be creative and have a high level of indispensable personal qualities, the most prominent of which are: -

- High scientific competence.
- Wide diverse culture.
- Intelligence and farsightedness.
- Self-confidence and abilities.
- Humility, tact, and good behavior. (Tafesh, 2004: 86)

Supervision of academic achievement

This type arose as a result of scientific progress in various human activities and in the field of education in particular. Supervisors began to follow scientific methods in evaluating teachers. However, educators and teachers reject it because education is a complex process that is difficult to limit and measure, and its results are difficult to measure due to the lack of reliable standards. He also considers the teacher to be just a god who works according to a specific system, so there is no room for the teacher to innovate and be creative. (Al-Saud, 2002: 56)

Other modern patterns of achievement supervision in classroom management include

Academic supervision (various):

The development of this style goes back to Allan Glatthorn and is based on the hypothesis (since learners are different, there must be diversity in achievement supervision) and seeks to benefit from other supervision methods and adapt them to suit the most significant possible number of teachers, providing them with several supervision processes and activities so that each person can A teacher can choose what suits him and achieves his academic and professional growth, which consists of three options as follows: -

A - Intensive development: - It takes place in eight steps: (the introductory meeting, the meeting before the classroom observation, the diagnostic classroom observation, the analysis of the diagnostic observation, the analytical review meeting, the training session, the focused observation and the focused analytical review meeting). These steps are complex and time-consuming, but they are applied to a small group of teachers.

B - Collaborative professional growth: - It is nurturing the growth of teachers through regular cooperation among colleagues, and it has several forms, including: -

- Peer-supervised training (peer training).
- Educational meetings.
- Curriculum development.
- Field research.

C—Self-growth: It is a professional educational growth process in which the teacher works alone to develop himself. The teacher sets one or more goals for a period of one year and sets a plan to achieve these goals. The teacher then implements the plan and, in the end, evaluates and gives a report on his growth. The role of the supervisor here is Support, not direct intervention.

Direct academic supervision

The mechanisms of achievement supervision that have taken hold in our supervisory reality make part of the educational supervisor's tasks linked to classroom administrative follow-up, making it difficult for him to carry out his technical work satisfactorily. Likewise, about the visits of the educational supervisor, it is certain that more than short, spaced visits are needed to help the teacher grow. The supervisor visiting the teacher with one or two visits a year is not practical in developing the learners, so the supervisor's goal in achieving the learners' level must be: "Working over the long term to bring about continuous professional growth for the teacher, and development in the educational environment of the school in general." From here came the idea of a direct modern achievement supervision mechanism for the school through the educational supervisor and the coordinating class director, where, in addition to his work in the field of specialization, he generally supervises all aspects of work in a specific group of schools and targets them as – collectively – the unit of developmental work of the educational supervisor, and writes periodic reports, for each school. (Badaoud, 2009: 26-27).

The study (Al-Dosari, 2008) aimed to know the role of the achievement supervisor in raising the efficiency of the job performance of art education teachers. The study sample consisted of (45) teachers. The study used the questionnaire to collect information that serves the study's objectives. The results showed that there are deficiencies in some supervisors. In directing art education, teachers should separate each class separately in the preparation book, use educational methods, pay attention to continuous evaluation, and not pay attention to the supervisor's achievement report.

A study of Tim (2009) aimed to identify the reality of the classroom practices of the classroom director in the governorates of northern Palestine from the point of view of male and female teachers. The study sample consisted of (391) male and female teachers distributed over four governorates (Nablus et al.). (Jenin) designed a questionnaire that covered supervisory practices. The results of the study indicated, in general, that the reality of supervisory practices of the educational supervisor in public schools in the northern governorates of Palestine from the point of view of teachers was weak and that the reality of supervisory practices differed according to the academic qualification, educational stage, and place of residence.

A study conducted by Abu Shaheen (2011) aims to determine the extent to which the educational mentor contributes to helping learners of the first cycle of primary education acquire the following professional growth skills: the skill of planning teaching, the skill of applying appropriate teaching methods, the skill of using educational techniques, and the skill of classroom management. Academic, the skill of evaluating students and identifying teachers' opinions regarding the contribution of educational mentors to their professional growth and the impact of the following variables: gender, academic and educational qualifications, experience in teaching, and submitting proposals that could increase the contribution of educational mentors to teachers' professional growth from the teachers' point of view, a sample was formed. The study included (173) male and female teachers. (138) female teachers and (35) male

teachers, with a ratio of (9%) from the original community of each in Kenitra Governorate. A questionnaire consisting of (60) items was applied to them. The researcher used the descriptive analytical method to answer the research questions. The study resulted in the following results: The degree of the educational mentor's contribution to the academic growth of learners on the questionnaire areas as a whole is moderate. There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance specified in the study in the averages of male and female teachers' answers related to the extent of the educational mentors' contribution to the professional growth of teachers due to the gender variable, as well as the presence of significant differences. Statistical significance at the level of significance in the answers of learners who have the qualifications for primary education and the presence of statistically significant differences at the significance level in the learners' answers to the areas of the questionnaire, all of which are related to the extent to which educational mentors contribute to the academic growth of learners due to the variable of experience in favor of male and female teachers who have a high level of achievement, using a test. Schiffe, for the experience variable, showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the field of teaching planning skills as well. The learners also presented a set of suggestions that could increase educational mentors' contribution to learners' academic growth from their point of view, related to modern educational techniques and teaching methods, the field of evaluating learners' work, and relationships. Humanity is the efficiency of the educational mentor in his work and his ability to help learners achieve growth in their students.

Al-Louh (2012) aimed to identify the degree of improvement in evolutionary educational supervision in effective classroom management of the teaching practices of Arabic language teachers in UNRWA schools while revealing the impact of the study variables on the opinions of Arabic language teachers in the degree of improvement as a result of evolutionary educational supervision. To achieve the aim of the study, A scale was constructed consisting of (62) statements distributed over three axes: the first: developmental supervision and teaching planning practices, the second: developmental supervision and teaching implementation practices, and the third: developmental supervision and teaching evaluation practices. The researcher used the descriptive approach, as the study sample amounted to (164).) male and female UNRWA teachers, who were chosen randomly. The study reached results, the most important of which is that evolutionary educational supervision improves the teaching practices of Arabic language teachers to a very great degree, and there are no statistically significant differences in the degree of improvement due to the variable gender and stage. Educational, while statistically significant differences are attributed to the variable years of service. Among the most important recommendations of the study is holding training courses for educational supervisors to develop their skills in the field of using developmental supervision in their supervisory practices so that teachers can improve their performance.

Results

After the researcher has finished collecting the questionnaire forms from the research sample, he will present in this chapter the results that are reached in light of the research objective (the role of classroom management skill in directing achievement guidance among secondary school students) through the use of appropriate statistical methods (the weighted mean), to know and determine the weighted mean for each

paragraph of the questionnaire, and the percentage weight to determine the percentage for each paragraph as shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. The Results of Research

No	Paragraph sequence in the questionnaire	Descending sequence according to the weighted mean	Paragraph	Weighted mean	Percentage weight
1	8	1	He undertakes the process of effective and fruitful management within the classroom and works to make the learners one team, all of whom have a specific goal of understanding and applying the lesson.	2.9	97%
2	6	2	He is directed to work on transparency and flexibility in classroom management and involve all learners in the activity.	2.8	95%
3	9	2	It gives sufficient guidance to achieve attention and focus among learners and consider individual differences.	2.8	95%
4	1	3	Effective classroom management, which involves class control, commitment, and arousing motivation to learn, is a primary goal in delivering the material to the learner with all care and honesty.	5.7	91%
5	2	4	He undertakes the continuous evaluation process to provide feedback to all learners and help them achieve the specified goals, the most important of which is increasing cognitive achievement.	2.7	91%
6	12	4	It detects the weak points of learners and directs the improvement of the appropriate academic achievement process.	2.7	91%
7	4	4	Assisting and contributing to change according to the changes in the subject within the classroom	2.6	86%
8	3	5	Classroom management guides me to methods and approaches in management and education that achieve the desired and fruitful goals.	2.5	86%
9	7	5	Implementing strategic plans is necessary to achieve classroom management and education goals.	2.5	86%

10	11	5	He writes the basic concepts of the lesson clearly on the board, asks questions, and assigns roles to all learners.	2.5	86%
11	5	6	It provides fruitful advice and guidance within the classroom. It alerts the learner to the importance of understanding and comprehending, then applying the complete understanding and mastery of it, and that what the student has learned today will be needed tomorrow in advanced stages.	2.4	80%
12	10	7	It encourages self-development, respects the opinions of others, and instills within the hearts of learners the love of discovery, solving problems, self-reliance, and avoiding dependence.	2.2	75%

Discussion

It was occupied by paragraph (8), which had a weighted mean of (2.9) and a percentage weight of (97%). This paragraph emphasized that effective classroom management has a role in making learners work based on one team for reform in the administrative and educational process.

Paragraphs (6) and (9) occupied it. The weighted mean of the two paragraphs was (2.8), and the percentage weight was (95%). The two paragraphs emphasized that focus, attention, and distinguishing between individual differences are prominent in achieving achievement guidance, which lies in guiding educational work with transparency and flexibility. In addition, the guidelines are based on fair investigation for all learners.

It was occupied by paragraphs (1), (2), and (12), where the weighted mean of these paragraphs was (2.7), and the percentage weight was (91%). These paragraphs emphasized the role of the skill of class control through the process of class control, arousing the learner's motivation and providing feedback. Detecting the learner's strengths and weaknesses is considered one of the essential matters in increasing the learner's academic achievement in the secondary stage, which is done through good evidence through which the feedback process is carried out to achieve the desired goals, in addition to detecting, diagnosing and treating weak points so that guidance can be directed towards achievement guidance. And fruitful improvement.

It was occupied by paragraph (4), where its weighted mean was (2.6) and the percentage weight was (86%). This paragraph emphasized the provision of assistance that contributes to change according to the variables of the educational and pedagogical process.

It was occupied by paragraphs (3), (7), and (11), where the weighted mean of the paragraphs was (2.5) and the percentage weight was (84%). These paragraphs emphasized the role of educational supervision through guidance towards modern methods and methods, in addition to following up on the implementation of strategic plans, including those suitable for achieving goals. In addition, the conditions of the human element in the educational process must be considered.

It was occupied by paragraph (5), where its weighted mean was (2.4) and the percentage weight was (8%). This paragraph confirmed that the skill of classroom management guides the teacher to provide methods and approaches in classroom management and the process of implementing plans within the classroom in a way that achieves the desired and fruitful goals and taking care to write the basic concepts of the lesson should be clearly explained by the patient, directing questions, and giving a role to all learners for fruitful strategic planning.

It was occupied by paragraph (10), where its weighted mean was (2.2) and the percentage weight was (75%). This paragraph emphasized that the teacher undertakes the task of encouraging through achievement guidance, providing self-development, respecting the opinion of others, and instilling in the hearts of learners the love of discovery, solving problems, self-reliance, and staying away from dependency.

Conclusion

Contemporary global trends in classroom management have confirmed several data and indicators, the most prominent of which is the diversity of its types, such as participatory, democratic, clinical, and comprehensive management, and the multiplicity of its functions between planning, directing, training, and evaluation, as well as the inclusion of its tasks in achieving professional growth for learners and developing their ability to memorize and retrieve, and its following many collective and individual methods, and investing in the dimensions and achievements of scientific and technological progress in directing the learner's achievement guidance, containing the learner, and taking him by the hand into the world of comprehension, perception, understanding, and fruitful and purposeful application in the process of interpreting the lesson topics and the possibility of mastering them.

The results of the field study in this current research indicated in one of the paragraphs of the questionnaire that it ranked first. This paragraph confirmed that classroom management has a role in the process of fruitful formative evaluation for the sake of reform in the administrative and educational process, guiding the learner to achieve the desired goals, staying away from the routine and hostile atmosphere, and directing the learner to A classroom environment full of excitement, suspense, and encouragement, reaching the level of mastery in understanding.

The results of the field study in this research indicated that one of the paragraphs of the same questionnaire ranked seventh and last. This paragraph emphasized the role of classroom management in raising the learner's motivation by encouraging self-development and respecting the opinions of others, building the learner's confidence.

Despite the efforts made to develop classroom management in academic guidance in Iraq in terms of its goals, functions, tasks, and methods, there are problems facing educational specialist teachers in the large number of tasks assigned to them, the lack of provision of technical devices and equipment, and sources of information, the scarcity of their use of technology and information methods, and the lack of opportunities to the use of computers and the Internet in their work, which in some cases hurts low motivation in learning and a low level of academic achievement among students in the secondary stage.

Recommendations

In light of the results shown by the study, the study recommends the following:

Updating classroom management tools and activating the role of skilled schools with skills and competencies to ensure keeping pace with the rapid changes resulting from scientific, technological, and informational progress and accommodating new changes in society in terms of goals, tasks, methods, organization, evaluation, and follow-up.

Benefiting from contemporary trends in practical classroom guidance and management to achieve and develop the required performances of teachers and educational specialists in classroom management and organization in schools.

Encouraging supervisors and educational specialists to prepare educational and scientific research and studies according to multiple specializations, ensuring the publication of useful and superior ones from these studies, and providing guidance and advice on the importance of the one in charge of the classroom management process possessing all the necessary skills in order to deliver the material to the learner's mind in the desired manner, away from misleading and distracting attention and isolating the useful and the purposeful.

Working to strengthen the role of the school principal as a resident supervisor in his school within the framework of strengthening the relationship between school administration and classroom administration.

Suggestions

In light of the results shown by this research, the research suggests the following:

Conduct more specialized studies on the objectives of classroom management, its functions, tasks, methods, evaluation tools, the problems it faces, and ways to absorb the variables of science, technology, informatics, and the necessary competencies for supervisors and educational specialists.

Preparing a study complementary to this research to explore the opinions of school principals, their assistants, and members of educational and teaching bodies in evaluating supervisory work and ways to activate its role to achieve their professional growth and develop the educational process.

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